

On the 2021 Rio de Janeiro Charter

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UIA; 2021 Rio de Janeiro Charter; Architecture; Urbanism; Capitalism.

Introduction

The International Union of Architects (UIA), founded in 1948, is a global non-governmental architectural organization¹ responsible for the World Congress of Architects. Its 27th edition was held for the first time in Brazil, in the city of Rio de Janeiro, in 2021.

The **2021 Rio de Janeiro Charter**² is the definitive document of the Congress and stands as its official statement of conclusions and proposals for 21st-century cities. The Charter is structured around four “thematic lines”: *Diversity and Mixture; Weaknesses and Inequalities; Changes and Emergences; Transience and Flows.*

For analytical purposes, we reorganized the topics addressed in the Charter into four broader groups: *Society (or Misinterpreted Social Dimensions); Urbanism; Architecture; and Architects and Urban Planners.* This alternative classification, presented in the Summary Table and detailed in the Appendix, allows us to observe the relative weight given to each theme, based partly on the number of references within the document.

¹ UIA, 2022. International Union of Architects. Access on January 1st, 2022, available at <https://www.uia-architectes.org>

² UIA, 2021. Access on August 25th, 2021, available at <https://www.uia2021rio.archi/wp-content/uploads/UIA2021RIO-RIO-CHARTER.pdf>

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Reflections

Based on this reorganization, we can make the following observations:

- a. The large number of references to *Social Issues* (24) does not reflect thematic diversity; but mostly reiterate three central themes: reducing inequality, reducing poverty, and promoting social well-being.
- b. Throughout the text, capitalism and the Market are explicitly portrayed as fundamentally antagonistic to society — predatory forces that erode social well-being, democratic institutions, and the role of the State.
- c. Considerable emphasis is placed on diversity and on how it should shape architectural and urban practices
- d. The low number of references to the Covid-19 pandemic is noteworthy. The Charter merely states that the pandemic revealed social vulnerabilities, but it offers no architectural or urban strategies for addressing similar emergencies in the future.
- e. The emphasis attributed to education and knowledge—both generally and within architecture and urbanism— is surprisingly low.
- f. Conversely, the document places appropriate emphasis on the conflict between democracy and authoritarianism, as well as on environmental sustainability and on sanitary and public health issues.
- g. Unlike the *Social Issues* topic, the many references within *Urbanism and Cities* (35) correspond to a fairly wide range of ideas.
- h. As usual, *Urbanism* (34 references) receives far more attention than *Architecture* (17).
- i. Architects and urban planners as professionals are mentioned only twice.
- j. The words BIM and digital, for example, do not appear in the text, while “technology” — and sometimes “new technologies” — is repeated in a vague and loosely defined way.

Overall, the Rio de Janeiro Charter places much greater emphasis on *Society* or *Misinterpreted Social Dimensions* (82 references) than on *Urbanism* (44) or *Architecture* (17). It seems very unlikely that a 16- or 17-year-old student, after reading this document, would decide to pursue a degree in Architecture or Urbanism—unless his or her primary interest lies not in design, but in social assistance, which is indeed extremely important, but a very different field.

Architecture and urbanism are collaborative and socially embedded arts that require substantial investment and affect not individuals alone, but millions of people. They are, therefore, inseparable from their *social dimensions*. Even so, architecture and urbanism *cannot be reduced* to their social role or conditions.

In light of the Covid-19 pandemic, public health and sanitation naturally gained prominence, without any association whatsoever with the historically pejorative term “hygienist.” It is also important to acknowledge that, in the same degraded territories — such as slums and impoverished peripheries — where substantial investments in underground sanitation infrastructure inevitably disrupt the surface, it is both logical and cost-effective to seize the opportunity to implement urban redesign and landscape improvements, which can be carried out at comparatively modest cost and offer clear dual benefits for the local population.

The Charter’s explicitly anti-capitalist stance invites another reflection: if architects and urban planners are thought to possess the power to “destroy” the Market, should it not also be assumed that they have the professional capacity to make it a partner in producing good Architecture, good Urbanism, and better cities? Would this not be a more productive and effective path—one more likely to yield tangible benefits for society?

Finally, the name of the first thematic line, “Diversity and Mixture,” seems particularly appropriate. The coexistence, mutual understanding, and respect among *diverse* individuals and groups is, in our view, essential for building “welcoming and healthy cities, where diverse cultures and peoples can live together in peace and harmony” (the word *peace* notably appears only once in the entire Charter...).

Appendix – Alternative Organization of Topics

There are some repetition of ideas along the main topics 1 to 4, and inside of them. These are intentional and correspond to what was presented in the Charter.

1. Society or Social Dimensions of Architecture and Urbanism [82]

This title groups the topics: Social Issues; Capitalism and Market; Minorities and Diversity; Public Health and Covid-19; Participation, Democracy and Authoritarianism; Ecology and Environmental Quality; Knowledge and Education; The State.

1.1. Social Issues [24]

Themes approached *positively*: reduction of inequalities; poverty reduction; social well-being; coping with the contemporary phenomenon of migration.

Findings: increase in life expectancy; reduced birth rates; precarious refugee situation.

1.2. Capitalism and Market [3]

Capitalism in general and financial capitalism in particular are presented as having an “authoritarian and predatory character”, in addition to being hegemonic, “subordinating the State apparatus”.

1.3. Minorities and Diversity [6]

Themes approached *positively*: respond to the demands of more vulnerable groups, integrating issues related to income, gender and sexuality, race, cultural traditions and immigrants; downtown as a “place for expressions of diversity”; urban voids must be filled with social, economic and cultural diversity.

Themes approached *negatively*: racism, homophobia, xenophobia and misogyny.

1.4. Public Health and Covid-19 [7]

Findings: the Covid-19 pandemic as something that brings to light social weaknesses; “relationship between architecture and core public health aspects”.

1.5. Participation, Democracy, and Authoritarianism [11]

Themes approached *positively*: tolerance; “democratic management of the territory”; “grassroots participation processes”; “giving a voice to the plurality of realities and social, ethnic and gender diversities”; not “assigning high priority to absolute solutions”; “fostering discussion”; enhancing the value of natural, historical and cultural heritage assets.

Themes approached *negatively*: “depletion of critical thinking, with little political discussion”; disfigurement of democratic processes; “resurgence of autocratic regimens”.

1.6. Ecology and Environmental Quality [16]

Themes approached *positively*: sustainable urban development; rehabilitation of water resources.

Themes approached *negatively*: degradation of ecosystems; waste of resources and depletion of vital resources; climate change; environmental degradation; lack of drinking water.

1.7. Knowledge and Education [6]

Themes approached *positively*: education; respect for the arts and sciences; constructive relationship between the technical expertise of architects and urban planners and the wisdom of agents acting in the territory; [new] technologies meeting human needs.

Themes approached *negatively*: “submission of scientific and technological means to the interests of corporations”

1.8. The State [9]

Themes approached *positively*: collective urban space planned and administered by the State.

Themes approached *negatively*: State submissive to Capitalism or “Corporations”; absence of the State in deprived areas.

2. Urbanism [44]

Here we present the topics: Urbanism; Cities; Mobility and Transportation; Public services.

2.1. Urbanism and 2.2. Cities [35 total]

Themes approached *positively*: public space as a locus for social interaction; “cities adapted to contemporary demands”; fairer and more equitable cities; “re-significance of housing spaces and the city”; downtown area as democratic space and the place for expressions of diversity; respond to the demands of more vulnerable groups, integrating issues related to income, gender and sexuality, race, cultural traditions and immigrants; urban voids must be filled with mixed uses, public services and spaces, green areas, new technologies and diversity; urban slums and poverty-stricken outlying areas, supplied with infrastructure and public utility services; universal access to public services as means for reducing weaknesses and inequalities in society; urban design with democratic and inclusive solutions; “transition areas [...] without assigning high priority to absolute solutions”; “collective urban space that is planned and administered as a function of the State, through democratic and inclusive public policies, focused on combatting social and spatial inequalities”; the pedestrian as the main protagonist, with priority in spaces and flows; respect for the historical and cultural heritage; preserving the environment.

Findings: informal urban settlements.

Themes approached *negatively*: “extensive urbanization [...] [with] illegal trespassing and predatory urban occupancy of rural land, wellsprings, and environmental protection areas”.

2.3. Mobility and Transportation [5]

Themes approached positively: efficient means of commuting; multiplicity of modes of transportation, particularly public transport and active means of transport – walking, cycling, and others; responding to the needs of populations in their daily commutes; priority to the pedestrian.

2.4. Public Services [4]

Themes approached *positively*: universal access to public services as means for reducing weaknesses and inequalities in society.

3. Architecture [17]

Topics: Architecture; Housing.

3.1 Architecture [10]

Themes approached positively: use of local materials and local workforce; adaptability of the constructed environment; respect for the historical and cultural heritage; preserving the environment; tendering out public works through complete project designs; poverty reduction; social, ethnic and gender diversities; democratic public policies.

3.2. Housing [7]

Themes approached *positively*: to endow ramshackle housing with safer and healthier conditions, in addition to providing infrastructure; housing with appropriate locations; financing the neediest families; take into account plurality and diversity; permanent technical advice and assistance on social housing.

4. Architects and Urban Planners [2]

Themes approached *positively*: commitment to the community; constructive relationship between the technical expertise of architects and urban planners and the wisdom of agents acting in the territory.

The word “peace” [1]

“[...] welcoming and healthy cities, where diverse cultures and peoples can live together in peace and harmony”.

References

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Author’s Bio

Paulo Bernardelli Massabki is an architect with a master’s degree in Architecture and professional experience primarily in architectural design. He works at the Superintendence of the Physical Space of the University of São Paulo (SEF-USP) and previously taught at the Architecture and Urbanism College of the University of Guarulhos.